

ACOUSTIC EMISSION INFLUENCE OF THE SIZING INTERPHASE ON THE STATIC AND DYNAMIC BEHAVIOR OF ADVANCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

C. Mayer, M. Neitzel

*Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH, University of Kaiserslautern,
P.O.Box 3049, 67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany*

SUMMARY: In the present report, fabric reinforced thermoplastic composites based on different surface treatments were manufactured with a double belt press and examined by macromechanical evaluation using three-point bending and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). The influence of textile processing techniques on the composition of the coating either finish or direct sizing and thus on the mechanical property of thermoplastic composites was discussed. The application of direct sizings containing a lubricating and a coupling phase results in a reduced crosslinking density at the interfacial region due to diffusion and reaction of low molecular weight components such as lubricants and plasticizers evaporated at temperatures appropriate for thermoplastic processing.

KEYWORDS: Double belt press, fabric reinforced polyamide 6.6, finish, direct sizing, three-point bending, microscopy, dynamic mechanical analysis, energy dissipation

INTRODUCTION

Advancements in thermoplastic composites using textile reinforcements constituted a new class of composite intermediates. They can be described as tailored thermoplastic composites with UD or fabric reinforcements of glass, carbon or aramide fibers in quasi-isotropic or anisotropic arrangements to meet a variety of property and performance requirements in demanding environments. Compared with commonly available glass mat reinforced thermoplastics (GMT), they exhibit superior mechanical properties with respect to strength and stiffness. The selection of appropriate thermoplastics is another issue in customizing composite materials. Among suitable polymers are low-cost polymers (PP, ABS) as well as engineering thermoplastics (PA, PET). The manufacturing of such tailored intermediates is accomplished using a continuously running double belt press by the application of temperature, pressure and time. Afterwards, the semi-finished composite sheets can be postformed by automatized stamp-forming equipment into shell-type parts.

Besides the properties of reinforcement and matrix, the interaction of fibers and thermoplastic polymer at the interface has a strong impact on the physical behavior of composite materials. The quality of bonding at the fiber-matrix interface significantly influences the chemical performance in corrosive media, strength and toughness of composites. Therefore, an optimization of the fiber-matrix coupling with respect to both fiber wet-out and adhesion

between polymer and reinforcement is a primary requirement in manufacturing thermoplastic composites.

In numerous reports [1-3], the affinity of surface treatments on glass fibers to thermosets is well documented, whereas information on the compatibility of such interphase compositions with thermoplastic polymers barely exists [4]. Rovings with surface treatments appropriate for a number of thermoplastic polymers are commercially available. However, they are almost unsuitable for weaving purposes, since the fabrication of textile reinforcements makes specific demands on the quality of the reinforcing fibers. The aim of this report is therefore to investigate the affinity of distinct commercially available surface treatments to a thermoplastic matrix by macromechanical evaluation of samples manufactured with a double belt press.

SURFACE TREATMENTS IN TEXTILE MANUFACTURING

The fabrication of textile structures as advanced reinforcements in thermoplastic composites requires bundles of fibers either yarns or rovings to constitute a multidirectional structure. For textile fabrics or woven rovings, manufacturing is accomplished by weaving warp and weft on a loom to form a bidirectional cloth. Due to the high processing velocity, the fibers are subjected to heavy stress arising from frictional forces between the glass fibers and steel components of the loom. Hence, reduction of friction becomes a basic issue in weaving to avoid rupture of individual fibers and fluffing of the bundles and thus deterioration of the textile property.

Table 1: Comparison of finish and direct sizing

Fiber surface treatment	(i) Starch size - finish	(ii) Direct sizing
Advantages	High-speed weaving (600-900 y/min) Excellent coupling Designing of coupling agents for individual polymers	Preservation of fiber property One step manufacturing Flexible manufacturing
Disadvantages	Loss of tensile strength due to thermal treatment Additional processing step High quantity production required	Low-speed weaving (250 y/min) Size contains additional components affecting the coupling

The protection of individual fibers, textile processability and compatibility with the matrix is accomplished in two different ways: (i) A coating of size composed of starch, lubricants and cationic plasticizers is applied at the glass forming stage. For composites, the presence of these constituents negatively affects the bonding of polymer and fibers. Thus, the starch size is removed by thermal treatment at temperatures up to 600°C and substituted by coupling agents after desizing of the textile structure (finishing). The coupling agents either bifunctional silanes or chromium compounds form covalent oxane bonds or Van-der-Waals bonds with the hydroxyl groups on the glass surface and provide reactive groups to interact with the polymer [5]. (ii) A size consisting of a mixture of lubricants as well as coupling agents is applied to the glass fiber surface prior to the weaving at the glass forming stage to ensure both textile processability and fiber/matrix adhesion (direct sizing).

As listed in table 1, economical and technical benefits of two-step systems (starch size and finish) and direct sizing can be very distinct. Weaving of starch sized yarns is more efficient since the processing velocity is up to 3 times faster than that of yarns with direct sizing. However, the desizing procedure is costly and requires high quantity production to be efficient. Additionally, the thermal treatment at 600°C for a few seconds and subsequent exposure to temperatures up to 390°C for 72 hours to ensure desizing results in a loss of 10 to 15% in tensile strength of the fibers [6]. Table 2 exhibits the effect of reduced and preserved tensile strength respectively on the mechanical property of fabric reinforced epoxide and phenolic, where the number represents the change in mechanical property using direct sizing as surface treatment.

Table 2: Influence of surface treatment on mechanical property of fabric reinforced thermosets

Mechanical Property	Epoxide	Phenolic
US-style 7628, EC9-68, plain weave	Direct sizing (TD22) vs. finish (Z6040)	Direct sizing (TD22) vs. finish (A1100)
Tensile strength	+30%	+35%
Compression strength	+0%	+20%
Flexural strength	+24%	+28%
Shear strength	+30%	+30%

It is evident from above, that the deterioration of fibers due to the desizing procedure significantly affects the mechanical property of composites. Although textile reinforcements obtained from direct sized yarns exhibit superior mechanical property, the specific composition of this coating can be disadvantageous at elevated temperatures, since low molecular weight components such as lubricants and plasticizers start to evaporate at 150 to 200°C. This is not the case for finish-systems, where epoxide and amino silane based coupling agents are more durable at higher temperatures and components susceptible to volatilization were removed previously from the glass fiber surface.

Hence, it is assumed that manufacturing of thermoset and thermoplastic composites using direct sizings as surface treatments can be detrimental, since thermoplastic polymers require processing temperatures above 200°C. Components of the direct sizing may alter or deteriorate and thus negatively affect the interfacial bonding. For continuous manufacturing of engineering polymers such as polyamide processing temperatures exceed 250°C to melt the polymer and achieve viscosity low enough to percolate the fiber bundles. Therefore, investigation of the influence of pretreatment using finished textiles on the one hand and deterioration of the direct sizing at elevated temperatures on the other hand on the mechanical property of fabric reinforced thermoplastic composites becomes a necessity.

SAMPLE PREPARATION

A typical PA 6.6 matrix system, several commercial sizing systems and E-glass fabrics were selected as composite components for both microscopic observation as well as mechanical testing. The PA 6.6 matrix used in this study was supplied as 100 µm film by DuPont. E-glass yarn of 68 tex and 9 µm filament diameter was used to manufacture fabrics of 8 H satin weave US-style 7581 with 22 yarns/cm in warp and 21 yarns/cm in weft direction. Fabrics

were supplied with four commercial surface treatments either finish or direct sizing. Finished fabrics (A1100, Z6224) were manufactured by Hexcel, whereas yarns with direct sizing were provided by Vetrotex (TD22) and PPG (1383) respectively and woven by Verseidag. The coating content was 0.3 wt.-% for the finish and 0.8 wt.-% for the direct sizing. As far as known [7], the sizing composition as well as the product code and yarn supplier or weaver for each surface treatment used is listed in table 3.

Table 3: Surface treatments

Surface Treatment	Product Code	Type	Yarn Supplier/Weaver
Amino Silane	A 1100	Finish	Hexcel
Chloridfree Styrylamine Silane	Z 6224	Finish	Hexcel
Polyvinyle Acetate and Silane	TD 22	Direct Sizing	Vetrotex
Silane	1383	Direct Sizing	PPG

Thermoplastic composite intermediates were manufactured using the film-stacking technique where reinforcing fabric layers and thermoplastic films are combined alternately to a stack which is pulled continuously into the double belt press (see figure 1). Inside the press, sufficient pressure produced by a hydraulic system was imposed on the laminate. At the same time, appropriate temperature was applied in heating and cooling zones along the process direction to ensure: (i) melting of the polymer without thermal degradation, (ii) impregnation of the fabric and (iii) consolidation and downstream cooling of the laminate.

Fig. 1: Double belt press (DBP)

Using four layers of fabric style 7581 (296 g/m^2) and five layers of $100 \mu\text{m}$ PA 6.6 film laminates with a thickness of 1 mm and a fiber content of 50% by wt. were obtained.

EXPERIMENTALS

For a strong bonding of fibers and matrix to improve the mechanical property of composites two phenomenons have to be considered: (i) The work of adhesion is a strong function of the fiber wet-out and thus the real area of contact between reinforcement and polymer. Among other parameters, the difference in surface energy of polymer and fiber determines the degree and velocity of fiber wet-out during the impregnation process. Generally, the lower the surface energy of the liquid polymer compared with that of the solid fiber, the higher the

wettability of filaments. (ii) However, a perfect impregnation may result in a weak bonding of fibers and matrices since the degree of adhesion depends on the number and strength of couplings in the interphase.

Three-Point Bending

As a first approach to the compatibility of commercial sizings and PA 6.6, a three-point bending was performed. According to a novel testing method for thin thermoplastic composite samples developed by DuPont and the Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH, a span-to-depth ratio of 32:1 at a width of 25 mm was selected to evaluate the flexural property. The samples were subjected to a cross head speed of 1 mm/min. Flexural modulus was measured between a strain of 0.05 and 0.25% and strength was determined at flexural failure. As depicted in figure 2, the flexural property vary significantly.

Fig. 2: Influence of surface treatment on flexural properties of fabric reinforced PA 6.6

Considering that the samples are only different by the surface treatment, this can be ascribed to: (i) the degree of impregnation, (ii) the strength of couplings in the interphase, (iii) alteration of the polymer in areas near the interphase or (iv) deterioration of the fibers due to desizing. The effect of the latter was discussed previously regarding thermoset composites. It is very interesting, that in combination with polyamide the mechanical performance of finished systems is better than that of direct sized systems. This is in opposite to the results obtained for thermoset composites where direct sized fabrics exhibited advancements by about 20 to 30%. Hence it must be assumed, that the composition of the sizings used have a much stronger impact on the mechanical property of fabric reinforced polyamide than the deterioration of fibers due to the desizing procedure.

To investigate the effect of the sizing on the compatibility of fiber and matrix, microscopic observation of polished cross-sections of as-molded samples and failure surface after flexural loading was performed.

Fig. 3: Micrographs of fabric reinforced PA 6.6, showing cross-section of as-molded samples and corresponding failure surface of composites based on finish (a,c) and direct sizing (b,d). (A) displays a region of unimpregnated fibers.

Clearly from figure 3, the composition of the surface treatment as determined by the specific textile processing method plays a major role in impregnation and damage pattern of thermoplastic composites. The figures 3 (a) and (b) represent the worst case in impregnation behavior of the fabrics as a function of surface treatment. From a series of micrographs on the cross-sections of as-molded samples, direct sized yarns exhibited partial cracks in the center of fiber bundles as depicted in figure 3 (b) whereas finished fabrics tend to ensure better impregnation of the yarns as shown in figure 3 (a). Although it was difficult to distinguish the cross-sectional areas of samples different in surface coating by means of impregnation quality, it could be proved empirically that the specific composition of direct sizings penalizes polymer percolation into the yarns. Since finish and direct sizing are not only different by composition but also by weight content, the worse impregnation of direct sized yarns is either a result of low molecular weight components evaporating at 200°C or higher weight content of the coating. Looking at the failure surface via scanning electron microscopy as shown in figure 3 (c) and (d), the differences in using finished and direct sized fabrics are much more severe. Polyamide 6.6 in combination with A1100 or Z6224 exhibits cohesive failure of the polymer, whereas for both TD 22 and 1383 failure occurred at the interphase hence reflecting a change in the degree of adhesion. Accompanying above, it has to be considered that mainly the presence of gaseous evaporated components at temperatures above 200°C have a strong impact on the affinity of fibers and matrix, since the pure composition of coupling agents in finish-systems results in a fiber/matrix bonding stronger than the cohesive energy of the polymer. In contrast to microscopic evaluation of cross-sectional areas of as-molded samples, scanning electron microscopy on failed samples provided valuable insights into the damage pattern of fiber and matrix as a function of coating composition.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

Among a number of techniques for interphase characterization [1], dynamic mechanical analysis provides a sensitive and nondestructive measure not only of the molecular structure and motion, phase morphology, filler addition and fiber orientation but also a detection of the interfacial region [8-11]. DMA is based on the measure of two types of response to a low-strain periodic deformation which are : (i) an elastic and (ii) a damping term. For viscoelastic materials lying between purely elastic and viscous materials, the elastic term ascribes to the fraction of deformation energy stored in the composite and thus stiffness, while the damping counts for the fraction of energy dissipated as heat. In a composite material consisting of essentially elastic fibers, a viscoelastic matrix and an interfacial region, some of the deformation energy is dissipated. Energy loss occurs either in the matrix or at the interface. Since the bulk property of the PA 6.6 matrix used remains unaffected by the processing conditions, the change in damping can mainly be ascribed to the interfacial region. Hence, a composite material with poor interfacial bonding tends to dissipate more energy than a comparable composite with good coupling of fibers and matrix. Losses in energy are determined by the complex modulus $E^* = E' + iE''$ and a mechanical loss factor $\tan\delta = E''/E'$ where E' and E'' are the storage and loss modulus, respectively. Thus any increase in damping and hence increase of molecular motion and decrease in strength of the fiber/matrix bonding is reflected by an increase in $\tan\delta$ and E'' .

Samples were subjected to a force-controlled periodic flexural loading and the complex modulus and $\tan\delta$ were measured in a dynamic mechanical thermoanalyzer, Eplexor 150N. The viscoelastic property were scanned for a temperature range from -50°C to 220°C at a heating rate of 1 K/min and 10 Hz. A static load of 40 N in combination with a dynamic load of 20 N was used to stress the composites. In figure 4 the progression of E^* and $\tan\delta$ of fabric reinforced polyamide 6.6 with surface treatments of A1100, Z6224, TD22 and 1383 is depicted as a function of temperature.

Similar to the results obtained from static flexural loading, the complex modulus E^* is considerably influenced by the surface treatment. Additionally, the course of E^* vs. temperature provides some interesting data about the flexural behavior above glass transition temperature in entropy-elastic conditions in the vicinity of the melting temperature of PA 6.6 ($T_m = 260^\circ\text{C}$). Clearly from the figure, composites based on TD22 and 1383 sized glass fibers start to fail at temperatures beyond approx. 180°C whereas the finished-systems of A1100 and Z6224 reveal a well developed plateau between T_g and 220°C .

The normalized energy dissipation $\tan\delta$ also reflects differences in the interfacial bond strength. As the figure indicates, a pronounced peak of $\tan\delta$ at approx. 50°C can be resolved thus representing a glass transition temperature. Since glass fibers do not exhibit any T_g peak below 200°C , any peak of T_g can be attributed to the coating on the glass fibers and the polymer.

Fig. 4: Complex flexural modulus and $\tan\delta$ of fabric reinforced PA 6.6 as a function of surface treatment and temperature (static load: 40 N, dynamic load: 20 N, frequency: 10 Hz, warp direction)

Comparing the $\tan\delta$ spectra of figure 4, the degree of energy loss below and above T_g and the value of T_g may be related to the morphology of the polymer in the vicinity of the glass fiber and the relaxation behavior of the interphase. In connection with the microscopic observations on failed samples it becomes obvious, that the influence of low molecular weight constituents upon the composite property can be fairly serious. Several authors have published widely on the effect, that unreactive organic groups such as lubricants and plasticizers diffuse during the impregnation process to form an interphase with many unrestrained or free end groups, reducing the crosslinking density in the interfacial region [2,9,10]. This plasticized region of enhanced mobility of macromolecular chains then is a source of increased internal friction but reduced interfacial bond strength as it can be observed from direct sized systems (TD22, 1383). For composites based on A1100 surface treatment, a reduced $\tan\delta$ and peak amplitude indicates an improved fiber/matrix interaction. Additionally, the introduction of Z6224 results in an increased transition temperature (71.8°C) due to an increased rigidity of the interfacial zone. However, it should be emphasized, that the degree of viscoelasticity may alter from energy-elastic to entropy-elastic conditions as depicted by Z6224, where the energy loss of high modulus chloridefree styrylamine silane above T_g coincides with the damping behavior of low modulus 1383. The distinct mobility of chains above glass transition temperature suggests a difference in the ratio of covalent and hydrogen bonds for individual samples since the interfacial strength in entropy-elastic conditions is determined by the presence of covalent bonds.

CONCLUSION

The application of glass fibers for weaving purposes exhibits few characteristics which are distinct from those of reinforcing fibers used in filament winding, injection molding or pultrusion. For textile processability and compatibility with the polymer different techniques and thus specific compositions of the surface coating are employed to ensure both protection of the fibers during weaving and efficient coupling of fibers and matrix. It has been demonstrated, that the affinity of commercial surface treatments in fabrics to thermoplastic polymers can be very distinct and even contrary to the phenomenons observed among thermoset composites. For textile manufacturing a lubricating is required to protect the fibers from abrasion. However, such components start to evaporate at temperatures beyond 150 to 200°C. Since direct sizings are composed of a lubricating and a coupling phase, the temperature range required to process thermoplastic polymers penalizes the degree of crosslinking at the interfacial region due to diffusion and reaction of volatile constituents. The system of starch size and finish provides a pure lubricating composition in the weaving stage and a pure coupling composition in the composite manufacturing stage and thus excellent bonding if coupling agents are compatible with the polymer. However, this technique is limited to fabrics with a weight to area ratio below 400 g/m². Additionally, the desizing at elevated temperatures (600°C) deteriorates the fibers and provides a costly additional step. Although the utilized surface treatments are only recommended for thermoset systems, some conclusions on the composition of appropriate direct sizings for fabric reinforced thermoplastic composites can serve as guidelines to enhance the fiber/matrix bonding. In summary, the following conclusion have been made to benefit from the technique of direct sizings: (i) The content of components susceptible to volatilization at temperatures above 200°C must be reduced to such an extend where textile processability of the yarns is just ensured and thus effects on the interfacial property are minimized. (ii) Heat stabilization of lubricants in combination with (i) could further improve the interfacial bonding. (iii) Bifunctional groups either lubricants at room temperature and coupling agents at elevated temperature could diminish the problems of two-phase surface treatments.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung BMBF (Continuous Manufacturing of Tailored Textile Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites; 03N 3008)

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